

Review article

Relationship between chronic kidney disease and cochlear function: a review of the literature

Mohammed B. Fufore,^{1*} Abdullahi M. Kirfi,² Auwal Adamu,³ Abubakar S. Muhammad.⁴

¹Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Modibbo Adama University/ Modibbo Adama University Teaching Hospital, Yola, Nigeria

²Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University/ Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi, Nigeria

³Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare, Bauchi, Nigeria

⁴Department of Internal Medicine, Modibbo Adama University/ Modibbo Adama University Teaching Hospital, Yola, Nigeria

Corresponding author: Dr. Mohammed Bello Fufore, Department of Otorhinolaryngology, College of Medical Sciences, Modibbo Adama University/ Modibbo Adama University Teaching Hospital, Yola, PMB 2076, Adamawa State, Nigeria. E-mail: drbellofufore@mau.edu.ng

Abstract

Background: Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is an independent risk factor for sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL), "This review explores the relationship between CKD and cochlear function. **Materials and Methods:** Relevant articles from PubMed, Web of Science, Medline, SCOPUS, Google Scholar, and Clinical Key were identified for review. The selected articles were published from 2006 to 2025 and written in the English language. A total of 67 eligible articles on auditory function in CKD were reviewed. **Results:** Prevalence rates of hearing loss in CKD patients range from 28.0% to 80.0%, exceeding those in the general population. Cochlea and kidney share developmental, structural, and physiological similarities, making the inner ear vulnerable to CKD-related damage. **Conclusion:** CKD is linked to cochlear dysfunction through metabolic disturbances, electrolyte imbalances, and other factors. Early audiological screening in CKD patients is recommended to facilitate timely intervention and improve quality of life.

Keywords: Chronic kidney disease, Cochlear function, Hearing loss, Renal failure, Sensorineural hearing loss

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Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is defined as "Glomerular filtration rate (GFR) of less than 60 mL per minute per 1.73 m², for more than 3 months, with or without kidney damage".¹⁻⁶ Alport in 1927 first reported the association between chronic kidney disease and hearing loss, almost a century ago, where he described a case of familial kidney disease related to hearing loss.⁷ Other observations followed, indicating the presence of hearing impairment in many kidney diseases, including disorders in which no genetic disease was indicated.^{8,9} Some of these rare conditions or syndromes in which hearing loss is closely linked to CKD include hypoparathyroidism, deafness and renal dysplasia (HDR) syndrome, mitochondrial myopathy, encephalopathy, lactic acidosis and stroke (MELAS) syndrome and Branchio-Oto-Renal (BOR) syndrome.⁸⁻¹¹ Quick et al.¹² investigated the possible existence of shared antigenicity between the cochlea of the inner ear and the kidney in experimental animals and found a fascinating similarity between the kidney and the cochlea. The experimental evidence revealed a possibility of antigenically similar epithelial components of the two organs.¹²

The burden of CKD is huge, especially in developing countries, where most patients present to the hospital in the late stages of the disease.¹³ The prevalence of CKD in the community was grossly underestimated in the past.¹⁴ The World Health Organisation (WHO) statistics revealed that the death rate from intrinsic kidney disease in the year 2002 was up to a million, making CKD the twelfth major cause of death.¹⁴ The National Kidney Foundation estimated that about 20 million Americans have chronic kidney disease with another 20 million individuals having an increased risk of developing the disease.¹⁴ Statistics have shown that, in 2013 alone, there were 2.50 million patients on dialysis worldwide, and by 2030, the number of CKD patients on dialysis is projected to reach 6.50 million.¹⁵ The prevalence of impaired kidney function was estimated to range between 10.0% and 20.0% of the adult population in most countries worldwide.¹⁴ However, the prevalence varies across the globe. In America, the prevalence of CKD from various studies ranged between 7.0% and 8.6%.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

The prevalence of CKD in sub-Saharan Africa in a meta-analysis of 90 studies was reported as 13.9%.¹⁹ Available studies in Nigeria have reported that the prevalence of CKD ranged from 3.6% to 19.9%.^{3,14,20}

There are numerous potential causes of chronic kidney disease in sub-Saharan Africa, making the kidney disease particularly burdensome in the region. Chronic kidney disease can be caused by either communicable or non-communicable diseases; most common non-communicable diseases causing CKD include diabetes and hypertension while infectious glomerulonephritis, Human Immuno-Deficiency Virus (HIV) infection, Leishmaniasis and Schistosomiasis are common communicable diseases that cause CKD.^{3,4,19,23,24} These causes of CKD are very common in sub-Saharan Africa; for instance, HIV alone affects more than 22.0 million people in sub-Saharan Africa.¹⁹ This makes the burden of CKD in the region overwhelmingly high.¹⁹

Common signs and symptoms suggestive of chronic kidney disease include: nausea, vomiting, oliguria, generalised body weakness, fatigue, loss of appetite, chest pain, dyspnoea, pedal or ankle oedema, weight loss, and elevated blood pressure.²⁵ Hearing loss, tinnitus and vertigo are the most common Otologic symptoms in patients with CKD.^{26,27} Numerous complications associated with chronic kidney disease result in decreased quality of life, and auditory dysfunction is one of its major complications.^{28,29} The aim of this review was to explore the relationship between CKD and cochlear function.

Diagnosis of chronic kidney disease: The definitive diagnosis of chronic kidney disease includes proteinuria, glycosuria, haematuria, the presence of nitrites in the urine, elevated serum creatinine, and electrolyte derangement.^{3,5,14,20} The GFR is then calculated using the Cockcroft and Gault equation, and all those with a persistent GFR of less than 60mL/min/1.73 m² would be classified as having CKD, irrespective of the presence or absence of kidney damage.^{1,5,14,21}

Stage I kidney disease is classified as GFR of ≥ 90 mL/min/1.73m², Stage II kidney disease is classified as GFR of between 60 and 89 mL/min/1.73m², Stage III CKD is classified as GFR of between 30 and 59 mL/min/1.73m², stage IV CKD is GFR of between 15 and 29 mL/min/1.73m² and stage V CKD is GFR of less than 15 mL/min/1.73m².^{1,2,8,33,34}

Diagnosis of hearing loss: Pure-tone audiometry is the most commonly used method for assessing the effects of kidney disease on the auditory system. The diagnosis of hearing loss is made when the average pure tone readings obtained at 500, 1000, 2000 and 4000 Hz exceed 25dB hearing level.^{6,35}

Materials and Methods

A comprehensive literature search was performed across several electronic databases, including PubMed, Scopus, Medline, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, following the PRISMA guidelines. The search terms included: "chronic kidney disease," "chronic renal failure," "haemodialysis," "hearing loss," "hearing impairment," "cochlear function," and "sensorineural hearing loss." This review focused on English-language original research articles published between 2006 and 2025 that examined auditory function in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) and presented audiologic results. The initial search yielded 514 relevant articles. All articles were screened independently by the research team. After applying filters based on title, abstract, publication year, language (English), and full-text availability, 183 articles were selected for detailed evaluation of the full text. Ultimately, 67 studies met the predefined inclusion criteria and were included in the review.

Results

This review examined 67 articles, applying cross-sectional and case-control designs. Most studies were from Asia, followed by Africa. Hearing loss prevalence in CKD patients ranged from 20.0% to 80.0%, typically bilateral, sensorineural, and high-frequency. The cochlea and kidney share

similarities, making the inner ear vulnerable to CKD-related damage.

Pathophysiology of hearing loss in chronic kidney disease

Disease of the kidney simulates disease-associated loss of renal parenchyma, prompting compensatory adaptation by increasing blood flow and glomerular hyperfiltration, which maintains function at higher levels per nephron, leading to hypertrophy of glomeruli and tubules.³⁰ As a consequence of these adaptations, the kidneys' structure and function deteriorate steadily, reaching an end-stage renal failure within months.³⁰ It has been found that hyperfiltration and hypertension of the glomeruli are the major contributing factors to the deterioration of CKD.^{31,32} As peritubular vasculature underlies glomerular circulation, some mediators of glomerular inflammatory reaction may overflow into the peritubular circulation, contributing to the interstitial inflammatory reaction frequently recorded in glomerular disease.^{31,32} Any decrease in preglomerular or glomerular perfusion leads to a decrease in peritubular blood flow, which, depending on the degree of hypoxia, entails tubulointerstitial injury and tissue remodelling; thus, the concept of the nephron as a functional unit applies not only to renal physiology, but also to the pathophysiology of renal diseases.^{31,32}

Chronic kidney disease and the inner ear

The association between chronic kidney disease and hearing loss (HL) was first reported by Alport almost a century ago.^{7,36-40} He described a case of familial kidney disease associated with hearing loss in a 14-year old patient with a strong family history where all the members were affected.^{7,36} Since then, CKD has been recognised as a serious public health issue due to the increase in its prevalence and also its association with hearing loss.¹⁵

Studies have subsequently suggested a link between the kidney linings and the inner ear.^{6,7,8,33,37,38,41} The cochlea of the inner ear and the kidney have some membranes, held together by a substance called collagen, which are similar in both structure and function.^{8,38,41} These membranes aid in maintaining the chemical balance of the fluids of the inner ear and the kidney.^{8,41} These similarities make both organs vulnerable to the same substances, such as diuretics, and the association between many other CKD conditions and hearing loss.^{6,8,33} Various other aetiological factors have also been linked to hearing loss in patients with renal failure. These include hypertension, diabetes, electrolyte derangement, the use of nephrotoxic and

ototoxic medicines and haemodialysis (a treatment option for chronic kidney disease).^{8,9,33-35,41-45}

The prevalence of hearing impairment among patients with chronic kidney disease worldwide ranges from 28.0% to 80.0%.^{6,9,15,26,27,44,46} The prevalence of hearing loss among CKD patients in Nigeria ranges between 58.5% and 79.0%.^{6,26,47,48} The consequences of hearing loss in this group of patients are that the hearing loss can become severe over time, which in turn will negatively affect their ability to effectively communicate with other people, resulting in low self-esteem, social isolation, anger and depression.^{33,49}

Pure tone audiometry is one of the most commonly used methods in investigating the effects of kidney disease on the auditory system.^{6,43} Mild to moderate hearing loss is the most frequently encountered degree of hearing loss in patients with CKD^{6,9,15,27,33,35,44}, while sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) is the most commonly associated type of hearing loss in patients with chronic kidney disease.^{6,8,15,33,35,37,42} Patients with chronic kidney disease would benefit from early detection of hearing loss, allowing early rehabilitative measures to be taken.

Prevalence of chronic kidney disease and its association with hearing loss

The prevalence of CKD in Switzerland, Iceland and Italy were reported as 8.1%, 7.2% and 6.4% respectively.^{50,51,52} Studies from Asia and Australia revealed the prevalence of CKD as 6.6% in Singapore,⁵³ 6.8% in Thailand,⁵⁴ 10.3% in Japan,⁵⁵ and 12.0% in Australia.⁵⁶ In Zimbabwe, the prevalence of CKD ranges between 20.0% and 30.0%.¹⁹ According to Stanifer and colleagues,¹⁹ the prevalence of CKD in Ghana, Democratic Republic of Congo, Sudan, South Africa, Rwanda and Zambia ranged from 4.0% to 24.0%. The prevalence of CKD in Nigeria ranged between 3.6% and 19.9%.^{3,14,20,21,22}

The prevalence of CKD and its association with hearing loss has been increasing, particularly in developing countries.^{7,8,35,44} Studies have shown that the prevalence of hearing loss among CKD patients in India ranges between 28.0% and 80.0%.^{6,9,28,35,44,46,57} In Bangladesh, Rahman and colleagues⁸ reported a prevalence of 54.0% of hearing loss among CKD patients. Costa and co-workers¹⁵ in Brazil reported a prevalence of 53.8%, while in Nigeria, the prevalence of hearing loss among CKD patients ranges between 58.5% and 79.0%.^{6,26,33,47,48}

Jamaldeen et al.⁴⁴ reported a hearing loss of 41.7% among patients with CKD undergoing haemodialysis, compared with 15.0% in controls. In

Sharma and colleagues²⁷ study, the prevalence of hearing loss among CKD patients was 73.1%. However, Meena and co-workers⁸ found a low incidence of hearing loss among the CKD patients and controls to be 28.0% and 6.0%, respectively. Rahman and colleagues⁸ found a prevalence of 54.0% of hearing loss in patients with CKD while only 16.0% of the controls had hearing loss. In Nigeria, the prevalence of hearing loss among patients with CKD ranges from 58.5% to 79.0%.^{6,26,33,47,48} Lasisi et al.²⁶ in Ibadan, reported a prevalence of hearing loss of 67.0% and 79.0% in patients with CKD before and after three sessions of haemodialysis, respectively. They concluded that the worsening of hearing loss after three sessions of haemodialysis could be due to changes induced by haemodialysis or effects of the duration and severity of the disease. Adekwu et al.⁴⁷ in Jos reported a prevalence of 58.5% among CKD patients, compared to 20.2% among controls. Fufore et al.⁶ in Kaduna reported a prevalence of 57.5% and 20.8% among CKD patients and controls, respectively. Majority of studies on the subject have established a relationship between chronic kidney disease and hearing loss. Kohansal et al.⁵⁸ in a systematic review found that CKD patients on haemodialysis are at higher risk of hearing loss than those not on haemodialysis. They noted that prevalence and severity vary between haemodialysis and non-haemodialysis patients, influenced by factors like CKD duration and comorbidities.

Causes and risk factors of chronic kidney disease associated with hearing loss

Available literature has shown that hearing loss increases in patients with CKD as GFR decreases.^{6,7,8,29,47,58-61} A study carried out in South Africa by Govender and colleagues²⁹ on 50 patients with all five stages of kidney disease (I, II, III, IV and V) revealed that those with stages I and II had normal hearing thresholds while those with stages III, IV and V had shown varying degrees of hearing loss, mostly affecting the higher frequencies. This implies that those in the later stages of CKD are more prone to developing auditory dysfunction due to imbalances in creatinine, urea, and electrolytes. Rahman and co-workers⁸ conducted a study on the prevalence and patterns of hearing loss among chronic kidney disease patients of various stages in Bangladeshi patients, and the study showed that 6.6% of those with stage III disease had hearing loss compared to those with stage IV and stage V, with HL of 33.3% and 60.0%, respectively. Seo et al.⁷ conducted a large survey of 5226 participants on the Korean National Health and

Nutritional Examination Survey (KNHANES) to look at the association of hearing impairment with chronic kidney disease and they reported that 46.0% of those with stage III and above (i.e. GFR <60 ml/min/1.73m²) have worse hearing thresholds compared to those with relatively higher GFR ≥60 ml/min/1.73m² (i.e. stage I and II). Similarly, in a large population-based survey of 2564 participants, Vilayur and colleagues⁵⁹ assessed the association between reduced GFR and hearing loss and found hearing impairment of 19.0%, 28.3%, 54.4% and 73.0% in patients with GFR ≥90 ml/min/1.73m² (stage I), GFR ≥60 ml/min/1.73m² (stage II), GFR <60 ml/min/1.73m² (stage III) and GFR ≤45 ml/min/1.73m² (stage IV and V), respectively. Most studies on the subject reported that hearing loss increases with decreasing GFR.^{6,7,8,29,47,59}

The role of haemodialysis in the causation of SNHL is controversial.^{26,34,62,63} Some authors have reported a reduction in hearing threshold after haemodialysis, while others are of the opinion that there was no relation between the two.^{26,63,64} Risvi and Holmes⁶⁵ reported a patient with progressive impairment of hearing parallel to progression of CKD, peritoneal dialysis and haemodialysis and they discovered changes in the anatomy of the labyrinth (atrophy, oedema and collapse of the endolymphatic system); they ascribed these changes to osmotic-dysequilibrium induced by the haemodialysis.

Similarly, Lasisi et al.²⁶ reported 67.0% of the subjects had hearing loss at recruitment and 79.0% had HL after three sessions of haemodialysis and concluded that there was significant deterioration of hearing in CKD patients following haemodialysis. Adekwu et al.⁴⁸, in a different study in Jos, North Central Nigeria, on the effect of haemodialysis on hearing function in adult patients with CKD, reported a 69.2% prevalence of SNHL among subjects at recruitment and 76.9% after six sessions of haemodialysis. They, however, suggested that the use of ototoxic medications during dialysis and changes in the fluid and electrolyte composition of the endolymph may be responsible for the SNHL in the CKD patients studied. Fufore et al.³⁴ reported a hearing loss of 59.1% among patients with ≤10 dialysis sessions, compared with 78.9% among those with >10 dialysis sessions.

However, Thodi and colleagues⁴³, in their study of hearing in patients with renal failure, concluded that although the method of treatment for CKD may influence the disease's effect on hearing, the duration of haemodialysis treatment does not seem to have a significant impact on hearing. Other

studies have also shown that duration on haemodialysis treatment did not appear to affect the degree of hearing loss in patients with CKD.^{35,37} Many nephrotoxic drugs may be ototoxic as well because of the similarities between the stria vascularis of the cochlea and the glomeruli and tubules of the kidney.^{37,41,47,48,62,66} The cochlear duct and the kidney have physiological, anatomical, pathological as well as immunological similarities.^{41,48,66} According to Zeigelboim and colleagues⁶⁷, the cochlear duct is thought to be vulnerable to certain diseases (e.g., kidney disease) and substances such as antibiotics and other ototoxic medications, which eventually lead to disorders that appear to affect hearing in the higher frequencies.

Meena et al.⁹ explained that the kidney and the cochlea share similar physiological mechanisms, namely the active transport of fluid and electrolytes by the glomerulus and the stria vascularis, which may also share common antigenicity. According to them, these may account for similar effects of medications (i.e. nephrotoxic and ototoxic) and immunological factors on the two organs. According to Heidet and Gubler⁴⁰ some pharmacologic approaches have been tested in animal models and in humans with kidney disease for therapeutic intent, and cyclosporine was found to delay progression of renal failure in humans and dogs.

However, the immunosuppressant medication (cyclosporine) was also found to be rapidly associated with nephrotoxicity and thereby precluding its long-term use. Angiotensin-2 type 1 receptor antagonists and/or angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors have been shown to reduce proteinuria and preserve glomerular filtration in subjects affected with Alport syndrome.⁴⁰

Studies have shown that electrolyte imbalance, hypertension, ototoxic drugs, diabetes and haemodialysis are the major causes and risk factors of hearing impairment in patients with chronic renal failure.^{8,9,29,35,37,38,43,44,68,69} Available studies have shown that based on auditory brainstem audiometry findings, the main site of lesion is cochlear and to some extent, retro-cochlear.^{43,68} However, the lack of correlation between blood measures and hearing function hinders a detailed explanation of the mechanism causing hearing impairment in CKD.^{29,44} Getland et al.⁷⁰ tried to explain that, on the basis that low-tone SNHL is known to be a feature of endolymphatic hydrops and that hydrops is influenced by fluid balance (the glycerol dehydration test), it is possible that

endolymphatic hydrops may be part of the pathological process.

However, there was no correlation between fluctuations in hearing and weight changes during dialysis, and if endolymphatic hydrops were involved, one might expect such a correlation to exist as an indication of gross shifts in fluid compartment balance.⁷⁰ Meena et al.⁹, Fufore et al.³³ and Bendo et al.⁴² in different studies of hearing loss in patients with CKD revealed that patients with long-standing renal disease had higher chances of acquiring hearing impairment than the healthy controls, even after excluding other risk factors such as hypertension, electrolyte abnormalities, haemodialysis, diabetes and proteinuria.

However, Rahman et al.⁸ reported that 54.0% of subjects with CKD had hearing loss, compared with 16.0% of controls, despite an almost equal number of risk factors between the patients and the controls. Their study revealed that 69.0% of the patients had hypertension, 33.0% had diabetes and 27.0% smoked cigarettes, with the controls having almost similar risk factors of hypertension (68.0%), diabetes (32.0%) and smoking (30.0%).

Type and degree of hearing loss in chronic kidney disease

The most common type of hearing loss in patients with chronic kidney disease is SNHL.^{6,7,8,9,27,29,33,37,42-44,71} Possible causes of SNHL in patients with CKD include: hypertension, diabetes, electrolyte derangement, ototoxic drugs and haemodialysis.^{32,43,45,72} Sharma and colleagues²⁷ conducted a study on 52 patients with CKD in India, and they reported that, out of the 104 ears examined, 76 ears (73.1%) of the patients had SNHL and the remaining 28 ears (26.9%) were within normal hearing threshold. Jamaldeen et al.⁴⁴, also in India, conducted a study on 120 CKD patients undergoing haemodialysis and reported 41.7% SNHL among cases, compared to 15.0% in controls. A study in Brazil by Costa and colleagues¹⁵ conducted a survey on 80 patients with CKD and reported 53.8% had hearing loss and all the patients had SNHL. Fufore and colleagues⁶ conducted a study of 60 patients with CKD in Nigeria and reported that, of the 120 ears examined, 69 (57.5%) had hearing loss, and of these, 97.1% had sensorineural hearing loss.

However, Rahman et al.⁸ in Bangladesh found a higher prevalence of mixed hearing loss than SNHL in both subjects and controls. They reported in their study that 40.0% of CKD patients had mixed HL, and only 14.0% had SNHL, whereas 12.0% and 4.0% of controls had mixed and SNHL, respectively. However, they did not provide any explanation for

why mixed HL was the most common type of hearing loss observed in their study. Adekwu et al.⁴⁷ in Jos, Nigeria, reported a 58.5% prevalence of hearing loss among patients with stages 3-5 kidney disease with SNHL, accounting for 97.1% of cases with hearing loss. Similarly, Fufore et al.⁶ reported a hearing loss prevalence of 57.5% among CKD patients in Kaduna, with SNHL accounting for 97.1% of cases.

Most patients with chronic kidney disease have bilateral, symmetrical hearing loss.^{9,35,44,47,71} Reddy et al.³⁵ reported hearing loss at 4000 Hz in 53.5% of the cases with 48.0% of the patients having bilateral hearing loss while 5.5% had unilateral. At 8000 Hz, 63.5% of the subjects studied had hearing loss, 61.0% of which was bilateral hearing loss and 2.5% was unilateral.³⁵ According to Jamaldeen and colleagues,⁴⁴ of the 50 CKD patients with HL studied, 38 had bilateral involvement (though not symmetrical). Similarly, according to Fufore et al.,⁶ of the 57.5% of CKD patients with HL, 91.7% had bilateral involvement. However, Meena and co-workers⁹ in a prospective study on 50 CKD patients reported 28.0% hearing loss and that all of them had bilateral and symmetrical hearing impairment. Bains and colleagues⁷¹ in their study on cochlear function in CKD and renal transplantation also reported bilateral and symmetrical HL in all the CKD patients with hearing impairment. In Nigeria, Adekwu et al.⁴⁷ also reported bilateral hearing loss in all the subjects with hearing loss in their study. Hearing loss in chronic kidney disease patients most commonly affects the higher frequencies.^{6,8,15,29,35,42,44,48,73} Reddy and colleagues⁴⁰ revealed that higher frequencies were involved in 52.0% of cases while mid and lower frequencies accounted for 9.0% and 2.5% respectively. Similarly, Jamaldeen and co-workers⁴⁴ in their study also reported that higher frequencies (2 to 8 kHz) were involved in 77.5% while the lower frequencies (250Hz to 1 KHz) accounted for 27.5% of the cases. El-Anwar and co-workers³⁷ in their study also found that high frequencies (4000-8000 Hz) were the most commonly affected (64.0%), followed by mid frequencies (1000-2000 Hz) (20.0%), and then low frequencies (250-500 Hz) (16.0%).

However, Getland et al.⁷⁰ reported low- and mid-frequency involvement of 41.0% and 15.0%, respectively, in CKD patients before haemodialysis, and the low-frequency HL improved from 41.0% to 38.0% after a session of dialysis. They have shown that the low-frequency hearing loss found improved significantly after a session of haemodialysis. A study in Jos, North Central Nigeria, by Adekwu and colleagues⁴⁸ also reported

that the higher frequencies were the most commonly affected in CKD patients. However, in an earlier study in Jos by the same authors on the prevalence of hearing loss among stage III-V kidney disease patients, 58.5% and 37.3% of patients were involved at speech and high frequencies, respectively.⁴⁷

Available studies have shown that CKD patients with hearing loss can have mild to profound hearing loss; however, the majority have mild to moderate hearing loss.^{6,9,15,27,35,44,49} El-Anwar et al.³⁷ in Egypt reported that 43.7% of the patients had mild HL, 43.7% had moderate and 12.6% had severe HL. Sharma et al.²⁷ in their study in India reported 44.7% of their patients had mild loss, 42.1% had moderate loss, 10.5% had moderately severe loss and 2.6% had severe hearing loss. None of the patients in their study had profound hearing loss. Jamaldeen and colleagues⁴⁴ also in India found that 23.3% of their CKD patients had mild hearing loss, 8.3% had moderate, 3.3% had moderately severe, 1.7% had severe and 0.8% had profound hearing loss while in the controls, 5.8%, 5.1% and 0.8% had mild, moderate and moderately severe hearing losses respectively, none of the controls had severe or profound hearing.

Meena et al.⁹ also in India reported that all those with HL in their study had moderate to severe degrees hearing losses (between 50 to 75dB). Reddy et al.³⁵ reported 50.0% with mild degree hearing loss, 13.0% with moderate and 0.5% had moderately severe hearing loss. A study in Bangladesh reported 10.0% had mild HL, 30.0% had moderate, 40.0% had severe and 20.0% had profound hearing loss.⁸ Adekwu and co-workers⁴⁸ in their study of the effect of haemodialysis on CKD patients reported mild HL in 77.8% and moderately severe in 22.2% at recruitment. They also reported that after six sessions of haemodialysis, those with mild HL increased to 80.0% from 77.8% at recruitment, while those with moderately severe HL progressed to profound hearing loss.⁴⁸ The exact reason for deterioration of hearing loss was not stated in the study.

Otoscopy and tympanometry in chronic kidney disease

Otoscopic examination is used to detect middle ear diseases such as middle ear effusion by determining the appearance and mobility of the tympanic membrane⁷⁴ while tympanometry is an examination used to test the functionality of the middle ear by assessing the condition of the middle ear and mobility of the tympanic membrane and the ossicular chain by creating variations of air pressure in the ear canal.⁷⁵ Tympanometry is an important

test used to confirm otoscopic findings and define the middle ear function.⁷⁴

Although most of the studies reported evaluation of patients with chronic kidney disease with otoscopy, however, the specific findings of the otoscopic examinations were not explained in details.^{8,9,15,35,76} Tympanometry was reported in numerous studies, but the specific tympanometry findings were equally not reported in most of the studies.^{9,37,42,44,49,57,76} Reddy et al.³⁵ showed that 92.5%, 2.5% and 5.0% of the patients had types 'A', 'As' and 'Ad' tympanograms respectively on the right side while 89.5% had type 'A', 6.0% had type 'As' and 6.5% had type 'Ad' on the left side. None of the patients in their study had type 'B' or 'C'. Fufore and colleagues⁷⁶ reported that 55 (91.7%) and 57 (95.0%) of the subjects and controls respectively had type "A" on the right and 54 (90.0%) and 56 (93.3%) of the subjects and controls respectively had type "A" on the left. According to their study, type "As" accounted for the remaining except for two subjects with type "Ad" on the left and one of the controls had type "Ad" in both ears. None of the participants had type "B" or type "C". Kligerman and colleagues⁷⁷, in their study of hearing impairment associated with CKD, found four patients with abnormal tympanograms, but they did not specify the type of curve observed.

Conclusion

The reviewed literature shows a strong link between CKD and impaired cochlear function, leading to bilateral, high-frequency sensorineural hearing loss, with high prevalence rates ranging from 20.0% to 80.0%. Shared structural and physiological features make the cochlea vulnerable to CKD factors like electrolyte imbalance, inflammation, and toxins. Advanced audiological tools can detect sub-clinical damage early. This under-recognized comorbidity impacts communication and quality of life. Routine audiological screening in CKD patients is recommended for early detection and rehabilitation to improve outcome. Incorporating this into CKD management can significantly benefit patients.

Conflict of interest: Nil

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